

QA Software Testing Guidelines for Open Preprint Systems (OPS)

Based on ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119-1:2022

1. Introduction

These guidelines provide a structured approach to QA software testing for **Open Preprint Systems (OPS)**, ensuring the delivery of a high-quality, reliable system. The guidelines align with the ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119-1:2022 standard, focusing on standardized concepts and definitions to ensure a consistent understanding of software testing practices.

2. Scope

These guidelines cover the entire software testing lifecycle for OPS, including planning, execution, and documentation of tests. They are intended for QA engineers, software developers, and project managers involved in the development and maintenance of OPS.

3. Objectives

- Ensure the quality and reliability of OPS.
- Detect defects early in the development process.
- Verify that OPS meets specified requirements.
- Provide stakeholders with clear and standardized documentation of testing activities.

4. Test Planning

Estimated Billable Hours: 10-15 Hours**

4.1 Define Test Objectives

- Identify key quality attributes to be tested (e.g., functionality, performance, security).
- Establish clear and measurable objectives for each testing phase.

4.2 Develop Test Strategy

- Outline the overall approach to testing.
- Select appropriate testing methodologies (e.g., manual testing, automated testing).

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4.3 Identify Test Resources

- Allocate necessary resources, including personnel, tools, and environments.
- Ensure all team members are familiar with ISO 29119-1:2022 concepts and definitions.

4.4 Risk Assessment

- Identify potential risks and their impact on the project.
- Develop mitigation strategies to address identified risks.

4.5 Create Test Schedule

- Develop a detailed schedule, including milestones and deadlines.
- Ensure alignment with the overall project timeline.

5. Test Design

Estimated Billable Hours: 10-15 Hours

5.1 Develop Test Cases

- Write detailed test cases based on requirements and design specifications.
- Ensure test cases cover positive, negative, and edge scenarios.

5.2 Test Data Preparation

- Identify and prepare test data needed for execution.
- Ensure test data is comprehensive and relevant.

5.3 Review and Approval

- Conduct peer reviews of test cases and test data.
- Obtain necessary approvals before proceeding to execution.

6. Test Execution

Estimated Billable Hours: 20-30 Hours

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6.1 Set Up Test Environment

- Configure the test environment to mirror production as closely as possible.
- Verify the environment is stable and ready for testing.

6.2 Execute Test Cases

- Perform test cases as per the test plan.
- Document test results, including pass/fail status and any defects identified.

6.3 Defect Reporting and Tracking

- Log identified defects in a defect tracking system.
- Categorize defects by severity and priority.
- Track defect resolution progress.

6.4 Re-testing and Regression Testing

- Re-test resolved defects to ensure they have been fixed.
- Conduct regression testing to ensure new changes do not affect existing functionality.

7. Test Documentation

Estimated Billable Hours: 5-10 Hours

7.1 Test Reports

- Prepare detailed test reports summarizing testing activities and results.
- Include metrics such as test coverage, defect density, and execution progress.

7.2 Test Summary Report

- Provide an overview of the entire testing effort.
- Highlight key findings, issues, and recommendations for improvement.

7.3 Lessons Learned

- Document lessons learned during the testing process.
- Identify areas for process improvement and best practices for future projects.

8. Test Closure

Estimated Billable Hours: 5-10 Hours

8.1 Test Closure Activities

- Ensure all test cases have been executed or appropriately deferred.
- Confirm all identified defects have been addressed.

8.2 Final Documentation

- Compile all test documentation for future reference.
- Ensure all documents are stored in a centralized repository.

8.3 Project Review

- Conduct a post-project review to evaluate the effectiveness of the testing process.
- Discuss successes and areas for improvement with the team.

Budget and Payment

- Total Billable Hours: Minimum: 50, Maximum: 70
- Payout per Hour: \$15 (minimum) to \$20 (maximum)
- Total Payout Range: \$750 to \$1,400

Supporting Documents for QA Software Testing Guidelines for Open Preprint Systems (OPS)

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To ensure thorough and standardized QA software testing for Open Preprint Systems (OPS), a comprehensive set of supporting documents is required.

Documents Provided by the Client:

- **Requirement Specifications:** Functional Requirements Document (FRD) and Non-Functional Requirements Document (NFRD) are typically provided by the client. These documents outline the necessary features and performance criteria expected from OPS.

- **Design Documentation:** The System Design Document (SDD) and Detailed Design Document (DDD) are usually provided by the client, offering architectural and detailed interface information for OPS.

Documents Provided by the Tester (Vendor):

- **Test Planning:** The Master Test Plan (MTP) and phase-specific plans are developed by the testing team to detail the overall strategy, objectives, and schedules for testing OPS.

- **Test Cases and Scripts:** Test Case Specifications and Automated Test Scripts are prepared by the testing team to ensure thorough coverage and validation during the testing process.

- **Defect Management and Configuration Management Documents:** The Defect Management Plan, Defect Log, Configuration Management Plan (CMP), and version control documentation are developed by the testing team to track and resolve issues and manage changes during testing.

- **Test Environment Setup and Execution Records:** The testing team is responsible for preparing Test Environment Specifications, Environment Setup Guides, Test Execution Logs, and Test Result Reports to ensure the testing environment mirrors production and track testing progress and outcomes.

- **Review and Approval Documentation:** Review Records and Sign-off Sheets are maintained by the testing team to document approvals and ensure alignment with client expectations.

- **Metrics and Reporting:** Test Metrics Reports and Test Summary Reports are generated by the testing team to provide insights into testing performance and outcomes.

- **Lessons Learned Documentation:** The testing team captures valuable insights and lessons learned during the testing process to improve future testing efforts.

This division of responsibilities ensures effective collaboration between the client and the testing vendor, facilitating a robust framework for QA testing in alignment with ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119-1:2022.